

MODERN METHODS OF RAILWAY PROTECTION IN MOUNTAINOUS AREAS**Abdujabarov Abduhamit Khalilovich***Doctor of Technical Sciences, Professor, Tashkent State Transport University***Kholbekov Khokimbek Salimbek ugli***Tashkent State Transport University*

Annotation. The article deals with topical issues of railway protection in mountainous areas. The problem of sustainable operation and integrity of the road near mountain slopes was analyzed. The features of modern methods of preventing the destruction of the road in dangerous areas are highlighted.

Keywords: railway transport, mountain roads, protective galleries, retaining wall, road, upland ditches.

In the modern world, rail transport is rapidly developing. Hundreds of kilometers of railways are being built every year, including in hard-to-reach areas. Hard-to-reach areas include: swampy, permafrost and mountainous areas.

The construction of a railway in mountainous areas is fraught with great difficulties. People have been living in mountainous areas for a long time, and have always used roads for walking, riding horses and carts.

In areas of terrain with a horizontal surface, a more accurate method for calculating natural stresses is adopted, based on known compression dependencies. For hillside terrain of the location of the subgrade may apply approximate methods of calculation. The main stage of the calculation of the embankment of the subgrade is to determine the volume stresses and the intensity of tangential stresses with the identification of surfaces with the maximum values of these importance. For calculations, we use the finite element method (FEM), the advantage of which is the simplicity of obtaining systems of resolving equations and the possibility of thickening the grid of elements, as well as taking into account the inhomogeneous deformation and density properties of the soil material [1].

In conditions of steep slopes, roads are always prone to rockfall, avalanches and mudslides. People have always tried to protect the road from adverse factors. The methods of protection were simple – the construction of small retaining walls and upland ditches. Retaining walls are able to protect the road from rockfalls and landslides on slopes with a slight slope (Fig.1 a). Upland ditches are used as drainage ditches, they also protect the road from small stones and prevent the ground from sliding (Fig.1b)

These methods could not always protect the road. In this connection, there were difficulties in operation. It was necessary to clear stone rubble, snowdrifts and restore the ways of movement of people and goods [2].

Figure 1– Protective devices of highways a) retaining walls, b) upland ditches.

In modern conditions, railway protection is carried out at the design stage. Based on specific conditions, certain methods of protection are designed. These can be snow-proof and rock-proof galleries, retaining walls, fortifications of mountain slopes with metal nets, metal barriers to the movement of snow masses, as well as the laying of mountain roads bypassing avalanche-prone areas and areas with possible landslides and rockfalls.

Protective galleries completely block the road from the rubble of snow and stones. The gallery is a reinforced concrete slab (6) covering the roadway. The slab rests on a retaining wall (1) on the side of the mountain slope; the space between the wall and the mountain slope is filled with stone (7). From the side of the cliff, the board is supported by a system of racks (3) and girders (8); the racks are installed in

the columns (4). To soften the impact of stones on the reinforced concrete slab, soil (2) is poured with a slope. A profile element (9) is retained from the facade of the ground filling. Figure 2 shows a cross-section of the gallery (Fig. 2a) and a view with traffic.

Retaining walls make it possible to strengthen the mountain slope and prevent falling stones and landslide [3]. Usually, in mountainous areas, upper walls are used. Figure 3a shows a retaining wall made of stone laid in steel grids, such a wall works due to the forces of gravity. The advantages of such a design are its cheapness, resistance to uneven precipitation of the base, the absence of "wet" processes, ease of manufacture and not the ability to accumulate water.

In addition to massive walls, lattice flexible retaining walls can be used. They hold the mountain slope and are themselves attached to this soil mass by anchors. Anchors should be placed in the ground beyond the boundary of the collapse prism. Such walls, according to the method of operation, belong to the anchored retaining walls.

Figure 2 – Protective gallery a) gallery layout, b) gallery view

Avalanche-proof galleries, retaining walls and massive foundations belong to engineering structures for which the stiffness parameters in various directions are many times greater than at the base [4]. In these cases, the motion of the system under dynamic influences is determined by deformations of the base [5, 6]. Such structures can be modeled by a system of non-deformable bodies, and the ground base can be modeled by distributed elastic bonds.

Figure 3 – Horse retaining wall a) gravity, b) lattice.

Due to the sharply increased volumes of traffic, especially in mountainous areas, stricter requirements for traffic safety in our country and the vital need for uninterrupted traffic at any time of the year, avalanche-proof and rock-proof galleries on roads and railways are becoming increasingly widespread despite the high estimated cost and difficult construction conditions.

The simplest and cheapest way to protect the railway is the construction of steel grids. The grid is fixed with anchors embedded in the thickness of rocks. However, grids cannot always ensure the safety of railway operation.

The use of modern protective structures ensures safety and throughput on roads in mountainous areas. This allows you to use it more effectively.

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